

Sample Name: PP 1-5 μm

Material: Polypropylene

Size: 1-5 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 68% particles are between 1-5 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology with protrusions and curled edges
- $9.3 \pm 0.2 \times 10^9$ particles per gram
- $8080 \pm 100 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- Sample contains 16 wt% talc determined by XRF and 26% determined by TGA
 - Lower value through XRF due to unsuitability of XRF for determining polymer composition
 - TGA value of 26% slightly lower than manufacturer's specification of 30% suggesting that talc may have been released during milling
- Cl, P, Ca and Fe were the most abundant contaminants, all $< 1000 \mu\text{g/g}$
 - Ca, Zn and P are present in the stabilisers
 - Fe, Ni, Cr are present due to stainless steel
 - Zr and Y are present due to the milling beads
- No changes due to milling observed in Raman spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PP spectrum with no evidence of degradation

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_v : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_N : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D_V	D_N	N_w	A_w
8.35 \pm 0.10	6.58 \pm 0.01	5.57 \pm 0.01	4.96 \pm 0.01	6.36 \pm 0.02	4.28 \pm 0.01	9.3 \pm 0.2 10^9	8080 \pm 100

Morphology (using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) provided by TNO)

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Component	Concentration
C_3H_6 (PP)	83.6%
$\text{Mg}_3\text{Si}_4\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$ (Talc)*	16.2%
Cl	635 $\mu\text{g/g}$
P	425 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Ca	375 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Fe	329 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Ti	21 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Cr	13 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Zr	5 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Ni	5 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn	<2 $\mu\text{g/g}$

*Quantification calculated based on oxide structure, Mg and Si concentrations

Raman Spectroscopy (provided by Wessling)